

Difficulties faced by students in large classes at University of Sindh Jamshoro, Pakistan

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Abstract: The current study focuses on the difficulties faced by students in their learning and class participation, while sitting in the large classrooms. The present study follows qualitative methodology to dig out the students' difficulties. The research tool that is used in this study for data collection is semi-structured interviews with the convenient sampling. Participants were undergrad students from two different departments of University of Sindh, Jamshoro Pakistan. Analysis and examination of data was through Thematic Analysis

Keywords: Large class, class participation, learning difficulties

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Introduction

These days, having a large class is one of the most crucial issues. If we examine this issue from the perspectives of students, teachers, and parents, we will frequently hear that large classes are not only the cause of poor results but also of insufficient participation, fewer feedbacks, and no student achievement, which results in no motivation to participate in class.

When researching large class issues, the literature focuses mostly on the issues that teachers encounter in their teaching. In this regard, some have claimed that the issue solely affects the lecturers, while others contend that splitting a huge class into smaller ones won't have a discernible impact on students' involvement or performance. While the only widely held belief regarding small courses is that students learn more effectively and participate more in class

Large Class

Countries under development or developing are ones who encounter the large class most frequently. This research aims to identify the effect of large class on students' achievement and class participation at University of Sindh, Jamshoro, Pakistan. ATL (2009: 1) in Yelkpiri et al. (2012: 321-322) pointed that large classes not only affect the learning and achievement of students but these also increase the stress level in students.

Research Problem

In general, large class sizes in higher education are not only problematic for wealthy countries but also for developing countries (Marais 2016:1; West & Meier 2020:2). According to the available literature, less research has been done on the students' perspectives of university level at University of Sindh, Jamshoro, Pakistan, than has been done on the primary and secondary levels. Additionally, studies that have already been conducted tend to concentrate on teacher challenges rather than student challenges and how those challenges affect students' academic performance and class involvement. Finding the students' issues and how they affect their involvement in class and academic performance at University of Sindh, Jamshoro, Pakistan, is the main goal of this research.

Research Question

1. What are the difficulties faced by students in large English language classroom at University of Sindh, Jamshoro, Pakistan?

Literature Review

According to Ur (1996), there is no set number of students that may be deemed a big number. Furthermore, some instructors compare the current number of their students to those they previously taught, such as if a teacher previously taught thirty students in a class and now has forty students, he considers it a large class. Various scholars have assigned various numbers of students that are regarded large in various nations. According to Todd (2006), a class with more than forty pupils is considered a large class. Furthermore, research reveals that class size varies from class to class and topic to subject. Some professors consider thirty pupils to be a big class, while others consider more than a hundred students to be a large class. (Hatte, 2005).

Students get demotivated and lose interest as a result of the large number of students in class, and the large number of students prevents professors from moving freely in the classroom. The issues that arise in big courses have a detrimental influence on students' learning and involvement in class

Learning in Large English Language Classroom

Christensen identified various challenges that students confront when sitting in overcrowded classes in 1994, which have an influence not just on their academic success but also on their learning and class involvement. He stated that teachers in overcrowd classes confront several challenges, which has an influence on their teaching tactics and classroom discipline. He also highlights how executing activities in large classrooms is tough for teachers, as well as other challenges such as offering feedback to students, personalized attention, and effectively monitoring them while conducting huge language classes. Large courses cause issues for both students and teachers.

In 2006, Risley stated that language teachers in large classes confront a difficult time and a significant problem; for teachers, he indicated that offering critical feedback to students' writing critically, particularly long essays, comprehensions, and other writing activities. He also stated that language teachers face difficulties in large classes when implementing group tasks, pair work, and project-based work because all of these require time and efforts that cannot be achieved in a single visit to the classroom, as it all requires invigilation and efforts to keep the class running smoothly. Discipline concerns arise when group or pair responsibilities, such as loud noise and sitting arrangements, are assigned to them. Risley also stated that teachers must inspect and evaluate all students.

Management issues in large English language class

English language teachers in large class sizes face a variety of management challenges, including correcting descriptive writing tasks, discipline issues, individual attention, student accommodation or seating during class activities, student voice or noise level, and checking assigned and home tasks. It is critical to check through the student's work thoroughly and without missing anything. This is the most time-consuming process. It is critical in language to provide positive criticism to individual students so that they may improve. The instructor must be extremely explicit about the student's potential throughout this procedure. Language employs the "learning by doing" technique.

Andragogy Difficulties

The main challenges teachers encounter in large language classes are giving individual feedback, facilitating speaking and listening activities in class, and maintaining control over the class as a whole. Teaching in large classes and learning in large classes are both challenging in their own unique ways. Activities that involve writing, discussion in class, and explanation of flaws and weaknesses. Even providing students with any useful feedback is impossible. In this regard, Christensen argued in 1994 that role plays and playing pertinent videos in class are even more challenging in large courses because there are fewer resources available to professors for students in large classes. If we pay great attention to the language problems that students encounter, a long list would include sentence errors, grammatical problems, working on vocabulary, and perhaps even having trouble coming up with their own ideas due to inadequate attention. Christensen emphasized the need to take these issues into account so that students in large classes can also work on themselves. In order to keep things simple, he continued, teachers often assign the same tasks to every student in the class. This is inappropriate because it is impossible to assess every student's mentality by assigning them the same task, which may or may not be engaging for them. This causes issues with student learning and class participation.

Research Methodology

Qualitative methodology is used in research to better understand a situation about which little is known (Corbin & Strauss 1990). Qualitative methodology has been used to collect data in depth about difficulties faced by students of University of Sindh, Jamshoro, in large class. Data has been collected through semi-structured interviews containing open-ended questions from 10 participants of two different departments. 5 students from each department

Sampling and Participants

It is important for researcher to select the participants wisely according to the demand of research and study criteria. Usually, researcher chooses participants on the basis of their knowledge and experience (Cameron, 2005). For the current study participants were chosen on convenience sampling because it was convenient to the researcher. All the participants of this study were from two different departments of University of Sindh, Jamshoro.

Data collection and analysis

The researcher acquired data in this study using semi-structured individual interviews with undergrad students from the University of Sindh, Jamshoro, who fit the study requirements. All interviews were audiotaped with the participants' agreement. Thematic analysis was used to analyze data for the present study project. The data was analyzed and concluded using Braun and Clarke's (2006) model. Thematic analysis assists the researcher in understanding and analyzing situations from a close perspective (Marks & Yardley 2004). In Braun and Clarke's theme analysis paradigm, there are six stages to take.

The researcher first reviewed the transcript until researcher became familiar with it, then produced codes from each of the questions asked and most likely looked for themes. After looking for and identifying topics, the researcher began analyzing the data.

Findings and discussion

Description of Findings

Participants were undergrad students who were studying at the University of Sindh, Jamshoro, Pakistan. All participants were under the age of 20 years. A sample consisted of five male and five female students.

THEME 1: LATE ASSESSMENT AND FEEDBACKS

SUB-THEME: Teachers are unable to give timely feedbacks and assessment to students.

P1: One of the respondents said, because of class strength teachers only give feedbacks to those who go to them first, which are mostly those who sits at front because they understand lecture clearly and get teachers attention.

P2: Another participant said that, I always try to share but I get seat at back and teachers ask to share ideas loudly and this makes me fear of being insulted

THEME 2: SEATING ARRANGEMENTS

SUB-THEME: Improper seating arrangements because of overcrowded class.

P1: One participant added that, because overcrowded class makes us face difficulty in seating arrangements, because if we get late even just for 5 or 10 minutes we have to get seat at back in sitting at back in class with 200 students makes us to focus difficulty.

THEME 3: INDIVIDUAL ATTENTION

SUB-THEME: large number of students takes to no individual attention on students'

P1: Participant responded that to make students involve in class teachers always assign us group tasks, groups tasks are not often but for always, and then only few take part just to present best, others opinion are not considered and only one presents so other groups get chance, but this leads to no individual attention neither work on students separately.

Discussion of findings

The aim of this article is to explore difficulties faced by students in large classes and its effect on their learning and class participation. Findings from this study concluded that students are not getting proper attention from their teachers, neither they are able to participate in class because of over-crowd. Also that their seating arrangement is major hurdle which makes them to sit at back even if they do not wish to. Responses from students suggested that they prefer small class more, over large classes, because they believe in small class they will get individual attention from their teacher and also they will get feedbacks from them which ultimately help them in their better learning.

Conclusion

The aim of this study is to find out the difficulties faced by students in large class and effect on their class participation at University of Sindh, Jamshoro, Pakistan. Study revealed that students were not satisfied with the number of students in their class, they clearly stated that their learning is affected in a large classes. The findings of this study can be used

to highlight the difficulties and then solve those for the better student-teacher interaction and effective class participation

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